

CLASSIFICATION, PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF CHRONIC BRONCHITIS.

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***Abstract**-Based on the analysis of clinical data and the results of monitoring patients with chronic bronchitis, a concept was formulated about four main stages in the formation and development of this disease. Based on an in-depth analysis of the features of the stages of chronic bronchitis in terms of finding real approaches to primary prevention, a draft classification is presented. A large proportion of viral and associated infections in the phase of exacerbation of chronic bronchitis has been established. A schematic diagram of the etio-pathogenetic treatment of chronic bronchitis is presented.*

***Keywords**-chronic bronchitis, pathogenesis of chronic bronchitis, classification, "often long-term ill", etio-pathogenetic treatment.*

Introduction

Material for the project of classification of chronic bronchitis (CB). served as the ideas that we have developed on the basis of many years (more than 10 years) of dispensary observation, diverse research and treatment of a large group of patients, which are partially reflected in our publications [5, 9,12, 13].

The presented draft classification received some clarifications and was subsequently used in practical work. Her present publication, with appropriate explanations, is the purpose and content of our message. The comments on the etiological aspect of CB mentioned in the note are related to the fact that in the vast majority of cases [7] patients with CB turn to a general practitioner (pulmonologist) at the stage of a detailed clinical picture of the disease or at the stage of its obligate

complications (see below), i.e. e. at the III—IV stages of the disease [8,18], while the I—II stages of the disease, according to the negotiability data, do not reveal *sya* [7, 8,18]. For a practical doctor, it is methodically quite difficult to determine the infectious nature of an exacerbation with an indication of a causally significant factor, because it is impossible to identify a microbe isolated from sputum with a factor in exacerbating inflammation in chronic bronchitis. Specially studying this issue, we [10] established a large the share of viral and associated infections in the acute phase of chronic bronchitis. According to the pathogenesis of CB - primary (primary-chronic) and secondary (secondary-chronic). A banal example of primary chronic pathogenesis is the latent course of the disease (at stage I-II) in a long-term smoker, when, under the influence of regular inhalations of tobacco smoke, the mucociliary escalator (clearance) gradually decreases (suppresses) and, with the next acute respiratory disease (ARVI), a clinical manifestation of a latent current endobronchitis. Attachment of a bacterial infection (usually pneumococcus) [6, 8] stabilizes the infectious-inflammatory process. In a relatively rarer variant of secondary (secondary-chronic) chronic bronchitis, the clinical picture of the disease is clearly preceded by an acute, nosologically determined inflammatory process, for example, acute (protracted) bronchitis [15]. In this case, CB is like a second disease. According to clinical and functional data, we distinguish between chronic non-obstructive bronchitis (CNB), when; obstruction is absent; chronic obstructive bronchitis, (COB), when a persistent obstruction is detected, usually increasing in severity of functional disorders; chronic asthmatic bronchitis (CAB), when there is a transient (transient) obstruction for a significant time (years).

Differences between COB and CAP were based on the constancy of changes in the parameters of respiratory function (RF) and dyspnea in the first case, their increase in the dynamics of observation in COB and, conversely, inconsistency in CAP.

In the latter case, respiratory discomfort in the phase of exacerbation of the disease, a relatively higher ($\geq 5\%$) level of eosinophils in the peripheral blood, and extrapulmonary manifestations of allergy also had diagnostic significance. We considered HAB as a variant of preasthma [6]. In CNB, we identified two options - functionally unstable and functionally stable [4]. In the first case, for many years (more than ten. And possibly all life), a completely benign course of the disease takes place: there is no shortness of breath, patients rarely seek medical help. Satisfied with the effectiveness of the data at the time of medical advice on the treatment and prevention of exacerbations. In the second case, during the period of exacerbation of the disease, clinical and functional symptoms of obstruction appear [6] in the form of irritative or allergic bronchospasm. In the latter case, these symptoms are difficult to distinguish from chronic asthmatic bronchitis (CAB). In some of these patients, the obstruction eventually becomes persistent, i.e. they move to the COB group. According to clinical and laboratory data, we subdivided CB into catarrhal and purulent. Their differentiation was determined by the nature (cytology) of sputum and / or bronchial washings, the severity of inflammation according to the clinic, blood tests (neutrophilic shift of the leukocyte formula to the left, etc.) [11,14]. I would like to emphasize that the diagnosis of catarrhal chronic bronchitis (3/4-4/5 of the entire population of these patients) does not require endoscopic confirmation, while if purulent chronic bronchitis is suspected (cough with purulent sputum, relatively pronounced symptoms of intoxication), bronchoscopy is required. When purulent endobronchitis is detected, bronchography is indicated to distinguish between primary and secondary (with bronchiectasis) purulent bronchitis [7,11,16]. The frequency of catarrhal purulent CB, according to the literature, is 86 and 14% [7], 85 and 15% [16], 82 and 18% [17], respectively. The allocation of two phases of HB - exacerbation and remission is generally accepted and, obviously, does not require special explanations. Phase diagnosis is reliably based on physical and laboratory data.

The main complications of CB.

When highlighting obligate and facultative complications of chronic bronchitis, it should be noted that with. There are virtually no obligate complications of CNB, an optional complication of both CNB and COB is acute pneumonia, which usually takes a protracted course in COB [7,1]. In COB obligate complications are pulmonary emphysema, pulmonary hypertension, chronic cor pulmonale, pulmonary heart failure (LCF) [12,13]. Understanding a complication as such a manifestation of the disease, which, being associated with the etiology and pathogenesis of the disease, significantly affects the therapeutic prognosis and requires the appointment of special treatment. Understanding a complication as such a manifestation of the disease, which, being associated with the etiology and pathogenesis of the disease, significantly affects the therapeutic prognosis and requires the appointment of special treatment, we did not consider diffuse pneumosclerosis a complication of chronic bronchitis (COB): when small bronchi are affected, there is always diffuse pneumosclerosis and vice versa [6, 3]. At the same time, pulmonary emphysema and other obligate COB complications fully correspond to the above formulation.

Examples of the wording of the diagnosis.

1. Chronic non-obstructive bronchitis (functionally unstable). remission phase. As stated earlier (see above), the nature of the inflammation is dominated by catarrhal over purulent: 8:2, 9:1; therefore, if CB, from the point of view of inflammation, is catarrhal, i.e., the most common variant of the disease occurs, then the feature of inflammation can be omitted ; in this example, «chronic non-obstructive bronchitis...», on the other hand, with such a reduced formulation of the diagnosis, the catarrhal nature of endobronchitis is always meant. At the same time, the purulent nature of endobronchitis should always be reflected in the diagnosis, because this determines the characteristics of the treatment and therapeutic prognosis of this patient. 2. Chronic obstructive, purulent bronchitis. Acute phase

(influenza A, parainfluenza, pneumococcus). Complication: pulmonary emphysema, pulmonary insufficiency II degree. 3. Chronic asthmatic bronchitis. The principles of treatment of patients with CB, which we are guided by in our practical work, are schematically presented in Scheme 1. We point out that the elimination (stopping) of the main risk factors (for example, tobacco smoking, working in an atmosphere | of a high concentration of toxic aerosols) — is an extremely important condition for the success of treatment at all stages of the development and course of CB ([8,18]. Unfortunately, in the practical work of a doctor, this important condition for success is usually underestimated or simply ignored. A logical question arises: does this explain the very modest results of treating patients with chronic bronchitis by doctors in most cases? Prevention of this disease has some features at each stage of its development [8, 18]. So at stage I, the main condition for success is the elimination of risk factors that threaten the development of CB. ; at stage II, this condition persists, but additional relief of irritative cough and bronchospastic syndromes of prebronchitis is necessary, indicating an overstrain of the mechanisms of mucociliary clearance (escalator) [2]; at stage II, especially III and partially IV, suppression of the infection and the inflammation of the bronchial mucosa caused by it becomes important. The least studied in this regard is persistent viral infection. Based on studies conducted in our team, it should be considered that the clinical manifestation of such an infection is unusually frequent (≥ 3 times a year) exacerbations of the inflammatory process in the bronchi, occurring under the guise of frequent acute respiratory infections and acute respiratory viral infections. These patients in the practice of a doctor are allocated to a special group of "frequently and long-term ill" (FLTI). Disclosure of the individual characteristics of the genesis of their disease is impossible without a special virological study already at the relatively early stages of chronic bronchitis II-III, it includes brush biopsy of the nasal and bronchial mucosa, the study of paired sera in a serological reaction (RTGA), etc. In these patients, we often detected the

persistence of influenza A and parainfluenza viruses, as well as a decrease in the functional parameters of the cellular link of immunity, which was explained by the suppressive effect of the viral infection. The inclusion of antiviral and immunoactive drugs (rimantadine, interferon, interlock, etc.) in the complex of drug therapy for these patients allows in most cases to improve their condition and restore working capacity, i.e. is the main therapeutic and preventive measure in their dispensary observation.

Conclusions.

Thus, based on the analysis of clinical data and the results of follow-up of CHB patients we formulated the concept of four main stages of the formation and development of this disease: I- threat situation with the presence of risk factors; II- pre-disease (pre-bronchitis); III- unfolded clinical picture of the disease; IV- disease with obligate complications of chronic obstructive bronchitis (COB) ("complicated disease"): pulmonary hypertension, pulmonary heart, obstructive lung emphysema, pulmonary and cardiac failure.

Acute bronchitis (ABC) with a prolonged course (LB), which lasts more than two weeks, and recurrent bronchitis (RB) (inflammatory episodes - 3 or more times a year) with involvement of small bronchi in the inflammatory process with hidden or clinically manifest bronchospasm phenomena, clinical and laboratory signs of a sluggish inflammatory process are one of the real ways of CB formation.

As one of the variants of prebronchitis, acute bronchitis with a prolonged and recurrent course requires urgent detailed and comparative versatile study, because it seems to be a real "substrate" of primary prevention of CB.

CLINICAL CLASSIFICATION OF CB

№	Characteristic sections	Their headings
1	By pathogenesis	1.1. Primary 1.2. Secondary
2.	According to clinical and functional data	2.1. non-obstructive 2.2. obstructive 2.3. Asthmatic
3.	According to clinical and laboratory data	3.1. Catarrhal 3.2. Purulent
4.	According to the phase of the disease:	4.1. Aggravation 4.2. Remission
5.	For the main complications:	5.1. Emphizema 5.2. Pulmonary hypertension (PH) 5.3. Pulmonary heart 5.4. Pulmonary (P) (respiratory) cardiac (C) (Right heart failure.) (H)

PRINCIPAL DIAGRAM OF ETIO-PATHOGENETIC TREATMENT OF CHRONIC BRONCHITIS

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